

**THE ROLE OF APPLICATION TRAINING IN THE DEVELOPMENT
OF CHILDREN'S CREATIVE ABILITIES IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL
ORGANIZATIONS**

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Abstract: In this article, there are opinions about the fact that the identification of abilities in preschool children and their proper development is the main pedagogical task, and in the process of solving it, it is necessary to take into account the child's age, psychophysical development, educational conditions, and a number of other factors, as well as the application diagnostic analysis of the development of children's creative abilities is briefly explained.

Key words: Ability, application, aesthetic taste, imagination, perception, labor skills

We all know that among the educational stages, preschool education and upbringing is the most important period aimed at teaching and educating children from a young age, increasing their intellectual potential, developing them spiritually, morally, aesthetically, physically, and preparing them for school education. is known. From this point of view, a number of regulatory and legal frameworks have been developed in order to ensure the development of the preschool education system in our country at the level of world standards. In particular, the concept of the development of the preschool education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030, the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On preschool education and upbringing", the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On preschool education and upbringing" the adoption of a number of decisions "on approval of the state standard" proves that attention to the field of preschool education has risen to the level of state policy. In the development of such regulatory and legal frameworks, the importance of using the

advanced experience of foreign countries and the achievements of science and modern information and communication technologies is focused. In the above-mentioned regulatory and legal basis for the development of the preschool education and training system, the following opinions were expressed on the issue of raising a morally sound, intellectually developed person: - The purpose of the state standard is to organize the preschool education system based on modern requirements. to raise children healthy and mature in all aspects, to introduce effective forms and methods of education and training in the educational process, and to raise a morally mature generation.

In fact, the pre-school education system is the main link that prepares the ground for all levels of education. Preschool children actively absorb and acquire all the achievements made by adults. In this process, they discover the world of things within their imagination, and with the direct help of adults, they develop the actions, motivations, and abilities that are implemented with them. Basically, from this period, the independent activity of each child begins to increase in its own way. Mobility, imitability and curiosity are of particular importance among the outstanding characteristics of children of preschool age. It is a clear sign of their curiosity that they quickly divide things (toys) into parts and pieces in order to analyze their appearance and construction. In the preschool period, due to the fact that children have fully mastered speech and are extremely active, they have a need to interact with adults and peers. They begin to strive for a wider range of relationships from a narrow one. The need to know everything increases. One of the strong needs inherent in the nature of a child of kindergarten age is his desire to see everything as new and learn it in every way. It is this characteristic in them that motivates the formation of research and creativity qualities. Curiosity plays a big role in the life of children of preschool age and in their mental growth, interest is one of the factors that motivates a child to do something, just like a need. Therefore, children's interests are a complex mental phenomenon that reflects their cognitive processes. Realizing interests and abilities and channeling them in the right way leads to massive victories.

According to psychology, a human child is born not with a ready ability, but with a talent, the source of the realization and development of any ability. Ability cannot develop on its own, it needs a favorable environment for its development. The social and family environment is important for the development and formation of creative abilities in a person. The first creative abilities of children are manifested in the period of preschool education. Children should live in the world of beauty, games, fairy tales, music, drawing, fantasy, creativity. (V. A. Sukhomlinsky) From a psychological point of view, preschool age is a favorable period for the development of creative abilities, because at this age children are very inquisitive, they have a great desire to learn about the world around them. Parents and teachers contribute to the expansion of children's experiences by stimulating curiosity, providing them with knowledge, and involving them in various activities. Accumulation of experience and knowledge is a prerequisite for future creative activity. In addition, the thinking of preschool children is much freer than that of older children. Preschool childhood is also a sensitive period for the development of creative imagination.

Thus, preschoolers provide excellent opportunities for the development of creativity. And the creative potential of adults largely depends on how these opportunities were used in childhood. In pre-school educational organizations, the child joins the children's team from the age of 3. The educator ensures the development of their creative abilities, knowledge, skills and abilities related to age characteristics during the activities and trainings organized during the day. For this, the educator and pedagogue must be a knowledgeable, talented, inquisitive creator who works tirelessly on himself. In pre-school educational organizations, activities such as staging, painting, making things from clay or plasticine, and appliqué help children develop their creative abilities.

Application training is of great importance in the all-round development of children. It awakens children's imagination and fantasy, activates observation, develops attention and imagination, will, develops hand skills, shape perception, aiming, color perception. According to scientists, people can distinguish 1300 different

colors at their strongest color perception. By developing color perception, children's aesthetic taste is educated. Having mastered the technology of cutting, they perform works such as object, meaningful, decorative appliqué from paper.

The word "application" is derived from the Latin word, which means "to place". Application is a type of visual activity. The appliqué is single-colored or multi-colored. A uniform application gives a graphic touch, and a multi-colored one gives beauty. There will be artistry in it as well.¹

Application classes held in the preschool educational organization affect the development of children's perceptive abilities, help to educate them aesthetically and form their creative activity, as well as help to form work skills and the emergence of willful character traits in them. In the process of application training, the child gets acquainted with color and its gloss (shade), practices, learns to know the shape and structure of the object. As his understanding of rhythm and symmetry expands, he learns to aim on a piece of paper. Children practice many times with color and its combinations in application activities, so they can quickly remember and distinguish many colors and their combinations.

"Color perception is the most popular form of aesthetic perception." For this, as a result of its development, we influence the aesthetic education of children. On this basis, they learn to know and feel the beauty of form, rhythm and symmetry.

In application classes, children often interact with geometric shapes, as a result of which they learn to see the abstract appearance of geometric shapes in the objects around them. They learn to better understand the structure of complex forms, to correctly analyze and synthesize them. In the process of familiarizing themselves with geometric shapes, children learn to correctly identify the names of figures that are not yet familiar to them. For example, children can count the angles of a shape and learn that it has 3 or 4, and as a result, they will learn the names of shapes such as triangles and rectangles, and then they themselves will learn the names of independent polygons.

¹ Sh.T.Xasanova. Bolalarni sahnalashtirish va ijodiy faoliyatga o'rgatish. Tafakkur. T.: 2020y

In the application classes, the children's ideas about size and space planning and the skills to correctly plan the paper surface are formed. Children will learn words such as between, right, left, above, below, behind, opposite side, around, as they learn to place the shape in a logical and rhythmic way when gluing the shape.

Children learn many valuable job skills and skills in appliqué classes. They learn to glue neatly and orderly, to keep their workplaces clean and to work with scissors, which are a complex tool. All this prepares the children for the handicraft lesson at school. As a result of working with light and small paper forms, children learn to stop the speed of their movements. In the process of training, they overcome difficulties, although they are small, which instills willpower, endurance, and patience in children's character.

Voluntary application training is held in all groups of the preschool educational institution. But children of the middle group are given ready-made forms based on their content. In large groups, children cut based on the content they think. Children of 6-7 years old can draw a sketch of the content of what they will do in advance with a simple pencil, and then apply the details of this sketch.

During training, favorable conditions are created for the formation of such qualities as inquisitiveness, initiative, mental activity, and independence of a person.

a) emotional education - subjects and events, their properties and qualities
direct, sensitive introduction to.

b) moral education - in order to educate children with love for the best thing, it is necessary to use visual activity (application). And moral and volitional qualities are brought up in them, that is, to finish the work started, to work carefully and purposefully, to help a friend, to overcome difficulties, etc.

c) labor education - here mental and physical activity is combined. The ability to cut, work with scissors, use a brush and glue requires a certain amount of physical strength and work ability. Children's participation in preparing for activities and cleaning up after them helps to form diligence.

d) aesthetic education - sense of color - when an aesthetic sense arises from the perception of beautiful color combinations. The sense of rhythm appears when, first of all, the rhythmic harmony of an object, the rhythmic arrangement of its parts is perceived. A sense of proportion - constructive integrity develops in the perception of different buildings. Gradually, children develop artistic taste.

The conclusion is that during application classes, children's artistic taste and creative abilities grow, and through this they prepare for studying at school. Because children are inextricably connected with objects, they get acquainted with their unique qualities, shape, color, size and size, they determine their differences and similarities, which allows children to be educated and think figuratively. In their works, children reflect the events that are happening in their lives and society, they are pleased and excited about them. In the process of application, the qualities of the will are brought up in the children, such as completing the work they started, setting a goal and striving to achieve it, overcoming difficulties, helping their friends. Qualities such as helping children and working together in the process of creating teamwork; in the process of job evaluation, they develop moral qualities such as a realistic attitude of their colleagues to work, correct assessment, and being happy with their work and the work of their colleagues.

List of used literature:

1. Xasanova Sh.T. Bolalarni sahnalashtirish va ijodiy faoliyatga o'rgatish. Tafakkur. T.: 2020.
2. N.Kayumova. Maktabgacha pedagogika. T.: TDPU 2013y.
3. Nurmatova M.Sh. Xasanova Sh.T. Rasm buyum yasash va bolalarni tasviriy faoliyatga o'rgatish metodikasi. "Sho'lpon" T.:2010y.
5. Sh.T.Xasanova. Tasviriy faoliyatga o'rgatish. T:2020y.
6. Sodiqova O. Toshboyeva D. Bolalar psixologiyasi. "Noshir" T:2013y